

DEVELOPMENT OF MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN**Rakhmonova Ayshakhan Oribovna**

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Abstract. Development of mental development of preschool children is revealed. The main processes of intellectual, emotional, social and moral development of children are shown. It is revealed that intellectual, emotional and social skills of children of this age change.

Key words: preschool age, children, mental development, development, intellectual, emotional, social, moral, process, intellect, morality.

РАЗВИТИЕ ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. Раскрыто развитие психического развития детей дошкольного возраста. Показаны основные процессы интеллектуального, эмоционального, социального и нравственного развития детей. Выявлено, что интеллектуальные, эмоциональные и социальные навыки детей этого возраста изменяются.

Ключевые слова: дошкольный возраст, дети, психическое развитие, развитие, интеллектуальный, эмоциональный, социальный, нравственный, процесс, интеллект, нравственность.

INTRODUCTION

We must always remember that the future of our country depends on how the younger generation is brought up, with what spiritual qualities it will grow up, how active our children will be in life, what high goals they will serve, which we must always take care of. and fight for it to be healthy.

The future begins today. If we do not pay attention to the issue of education now, the future will be lost. Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and similar real human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything.

Teachers are responsible for the upbringing and education of the mature generation in all respects. We hope that this manual will help future teachers to study in depth the psychological characteristics of each age and apply this knowledge in their future teaching activities.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In ontogenesis, the period from 3 to 7 years is the kindergarten period or this is the preschool period. Preschool children considering that in psychology there will be very rapid qualitative changes into 3 periods: (3-4 years) junior preschool period, (kindergarten age), (4-5 age) preschool period, (middle kindergarten age), (6-7 years) preschool period can be divided into

periods (kindergarten age). The child is in the process of developing the world of objects and events created by the human generation enters into relationships with. The child is everything that humanity has achieved actively acquires and owns achievements. Objects in this world, actions performed with their help, language, engagement in relationships between people, activity development of motives, growth of abilities, adult this should be done with the direct assistance of people. Basically from this period, the child's independent activity begins to increase. Mental development of preschool children is one of the main stages of their psychology. The main processes of intellectual, emotional, social and moral development of children of this age are carried out. Mental development of children is divided into certain stages depending on the characteristics of their brain and central nervous system, and each age period is characterized by its own characteristics.

Intellectual development. At preschool age, children's thinking is not yet deep and complex.

Their thought process is mainly focused on one thought and action and is manifested in practical and visual-figurative forms of thinking. Children have reached such a level that some thoughts deepen and go beyond the simplest expression of views. There are limitations on how children can focus on several objects at the same time and how they can improve certain situations.

They often find it difficult to learn how to communicate, write, speak and other skills correctly, but they strive to learn as much as possible. **Emotional development.** Preschoolers develop internal feelings and the ability to manage them. During this period, children begin to notice not only their own feelings, but also the feelings of others. They are able to empathize with others and express their desires through gestures and physical sensations. Children develop resilience, joy, and a sense of relaxation, as well as self-control skills. **Social Development.** Preschoolers begin the process of social learning, which leads to social interactions, including relationships with family and others.

Children learn about society and social norms by interacting with the people around them.

Children at this age develop social skills through various games and team activities. They learn to consider not only their own needs, but also the needs of others. **Moral Development.**

During preschool age, children begin to internalize moral values. They develop ethical approaches to their actions and words, while understanding fairness, truth, and kindness to others.

During this period, children try to evaluate their actions according to laws and moral standards. **Application and Practice.** During preschool age, children actively master various types of activities. They improve their hands and body, learn to apply various skills in everyday life (working with paints, wearing clothes, playing with toys, etc.). These skills form children's permanent work abilities. **Factors Affecting Comprehensive Development.**

Family and society play an important role in the development of preschool children. The approach of family members, attention and relationships with them have a great influence on the child's psyche. Preschool educational institutions, teaching methods and characteristics of society also play an important role in the child's mental development.

Teaching preschool children should be aimed at mastering their complex movements, developing basic hygiene, cultural and work skills, developing speech, and forming the first rudiments of social ethics and aesthetic taste.

According to the famous Russian educator Lesgaft, the period of a person's kindergarten age is such a stage that during this period children develop patterns of character traits and the foundations of moral character.

One of the striking features of preschool children is their mobility and imitation. The basic law of children's nature can be expressed as follows: a child requires continuous activity, but he gets tired not from the result of the activity, but from the monotony and chronicity of the activity.

Through relationships with adults and peers, the child begins to learn about moral standards, understanding people, as well as positive and negative relationships. A child of kindergarten age can now independently control his body well. His movements are coordinated.

During this period, the child's speech begins to develop rapidly, he feels the need to consolidate what he knows, in connection with the acquisition of news, to listen to a familiar story over and over again and not to bore him - a characteristic feature of children of this period. In preschool children, due to the relatively complete mastery of speech and excessive mobility, there is a need to interact with adults and peers close to them. They begin to strive for a wider circle of relationships from a narrow one. Now they try to play in a team with their friends from kindergarten and neighboring children.

The need to know everything increases. Another strong need inherent in the character of a child of kindergarten age is his desire to see everything as new and to learn it in every possible way. Interest in the life of children of kindergarten age and their mental development.

CONCLUSION

Mental development of preschool children is a very important stage for ensuring their proper development. At this age, children's cognitive, emotional and social skills change and lay the foundation for their future personality and success in life. The importance of interest in a child's development is that the child strives to learn as deeply as possible what is interesting to him and does not get bored for a long time doing what is interesting to him. This, in turn, helps the child develop and strengthen such important qualities as attention and will. Music as an artistic and creative activity in the mental development of children aged 3-7 is also very important. Through music, children learn to sing and perform rhythmic movements to music.

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